

The effects of Socio-Economic factors on various labour issues in the Rice Mill Industry: An Empirical Analysis

¹N. JAYAMMA, ²Dr. RAVINARAYANA K. S.

¹Assistant Professor and Research Scholar
Department of Management
Govt. First Grade College
Sindhanoor-584128, Karnataka, India.

²Assistant Professor
Department of Business Administration
Vijayanagar Sri krishnadevaraya University
Ballari-583105, Karnataka, India.

Abstract-

Purpose: The purpose of this study is to examine the key driving factors influencing labour related issues, such as work productivity, quality of work life, risks associated with work and employee turnover, among rice mill workers in Karnataka. A research was conducted to understand the effects of various socio-economic conditions (wage issues, gender inequality, health problems and working conditions) on labour-related issues. Further, the moderating effect of Covid-19 issues on the relationship between socio-economic conditions and labour-related issues was studied.

Design/Methodology: A quantitative and descriptive research design was followed for this study where a questionnaire was used to conduct an extensive survey. A convenience sampling technique is used to gather data from rice mill workers (n=200) in Karnataka.

Findings: The study found that wage issues, gender inequality, poor working conditions and health problems caused by the mill's environment significantly and positively influenced labour related issues. Therefore, the paper discusses various socio-economic conditions of rice mill workers. It was found that mill workers had to work for elongated hours without any proper breaks, meals or support. They did not get an opportunity for structured paid leaves and they mostly had to travel long distances to commute. Furthermore, they did not have job security and they mostly worked in a contractual mode. Less women employees work in mill industries and a substantial gender inequality was identified in payments and working conditions. Furthermore, the workers experienced substantial health issues that inhibited their work productivity and quality of work significantly. In addition, Covid-19 issues significantly moderated the effects of socio-economic problems on labour-related issues.

Research Implication: The study contributes significantly to the literature on labour policies and the socio-economic conditions of labourers from developing countries. Since studies conducted in this field are scarce, the present study would help to comprehend the workers' poor health and working conditions in rice mill industries.

Keywords: rice mill workers, Covid-19 issues, wages, gender inequality, poor working conditions, poor health condition.

1. Introduction

In 1999, the International Labour Organisation (ILO) initiated a few strategic objectives, such as promotion of rights at work, social protection, employment and social dialogues to ensure labour productivity and well-being of workers (Brill, 2021; Somavia & General, 1999). The ILO Constitution states: "...*whereas conditions of labour exist involving such injustice, hardship and privation to large numbers of people as to produce unrest so great that the peace and harmony of the world are imperilled*". Therefore, in recent times, the world has been moving towards achieving the goals of establishing decent conditions of work for peaceful and sustainable societies (International Labour Organization, 2023). However, recent reports demonstrate that inadequate economic security, lowered material well-being, lack of effort in closing gender gaps, persistence of informal employment and decreased equality in opportunity are experienced by employees all over the globe (International Labour Organization, 2019). It is

evident that the quality of work has not witnessed any significant change, despite the increasing number of employees in recent times.

Employment related to the production of rice has witnessed several challenges in labour related aspects. Rice is a major food staple all over the world and rice production holds a significant impact on the social, political, economic and cultural lives in most of the agriculture-based countries, especially in Asia (Rahman et al., 2023). Despite being an important part of labour economics, many global studies have not focussed on understanding the working scenarios of rice mill workers. Scarce literature in this field has showed that a majority of people belong to low-income backgrounds and earn their livelihoods by working in rice mills (Palit, 2021). Moreover, working conditions in the rice mill industry are not favourable in most of the countries. In most cases, the working hours are stretched to such an extent that labour laws are not followed (International Labor Organization, 2014). Even developed countries, such as Japan and the USA, do not follow any strict working hours for engaging people in informal industries (Kunitake, 2016; Leschak, 2008). Long working hours, unstructured leaves, and temporary and poor housing conditions are prevalent for workers in such informal sectors (Acharya & Christopher, 2022; Cockel et al., 2023). Furthermore, studies have shown that workers do not get any breaks during working hours and they do not get proper meals in factories (Tama et al., 2018). Previous studies have shown that rice mill workers are frequently exposed to grain dust and rice husks. Such long-term exposure makes them vulnerable to several respiratory diseases and causes adverse effects on various organs. Asthma, bronchogenic carcinoma, pleural thickening and fibrosis are observed commonly among rice mill workers (Fatima et al., 2016; M. Rana et al., 2018; Roy et al., 2020). Therefore, an overall perspective of the socio-economic conditions of rice mill workers needs to be understood.

Moreover, Covid-19 pandemic dramatically disrupted the labour market scenario all over the world and caused an economic downturn. The nationwide lockdown in most of the countries had a cascading effect on the lives and economy of millions of people belong to marginalised groups (Punia et al., 2021; Shah & Lerche, 2020). Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, many workers lost their jobs and were unemployed for a long time (Barhate et al., 2021). More studies are needed to understand the effect of socio-economic conditions along with Covid-19 issues to infer insights into labour-related problems.

The present study aims to understand various socio-economic conditions of rice mill workers in Karnataka. Scarce studies have found poor working conditions, low wages, and high health risks as the primary conditions of rice mill workers. However, no studies have tried to understand the influence of these socio-economic conditions of rice mill workers on labour related issues, such as work productivity, quality of work life, lower risks and employee turnover. It is evident from earlier literature that wage issues, working conditions and health problems caused by the working environment has a severe impact on work productivity, quality of work life and employee turnover (Edirisinghe & Manuel, 2019; Pereira et al., 2022). Such studies on the factors influencing labour-related issues in rice mill industries are lacking in developing countries like India. Moreover, it is important to understand the effect of Covid-19 pandemic on the lives of rice mill workers in India. Therefore, the relationship between socio-economic conditions and labour-related issues is investigated in the present study, with special reference to Covid-19 issues. This will help in the formation of labour-law policies for rice mill workers. Furthermore, such an approach will help to achieve sustainability goals for a decent work life for everyone.

2. Literature review and hypothesis formation

Effect of socio-economic conditions on labour-related issues

Wage inequality or stagnant wages, among other socio-economic conditions, have been thoroughly studied in labour-related issues all over the world in different industries (Alam et al., 2019; Kim & Choi, 2018). Maslow's motivational theory suggests that an increase in wages should enhance employee motivation and motivated employees usually demonstrate high productivity (Alam et al., 2020). Prior literature has showed a significant influence of wage issues on labour productivity (Coviello et al., 2022; Policardo et al., 2019). Apart from that, maintaining quality of work life has been observed to be significantly driven by the wages employees earn (Iwakiri et al., 2023; Pereira et al., 2022). However, studies have shown that only increasing wages cannot solve workers' problems, but occupational safety measures need to be enhanced to increase the quality of work (Iwakiri et al., 2023). Furthermore, employee turnover has been observed to be significantly controlled by employees' wages where in an increasing monthly income would result in a significant decrease of employee turnover (Edirisinghe & Manuel, 2019; Gao et al., 2019). Furthermore, the ILO has identified wages to be a significant part of labour policies where wage bargaining, minimum wage policies and gender pay gaps are addressed. Therefore, the effect of wages on labour-related issues would be investigated in the present study.

In addition, general inequality among workers is another notable socio-economic condition. Despite several reforms and policies addressing gender inequality in the workplace, gender gap problems are still encountered in many places. Such gender gaps are often observed for higher designated job profiles (Nelson et al., 2023). While women are making their place in professional positions, they are underrepresented in leadership roles or equity partnership roles (Bennett et al., 2019; Nelson et al., 2023; Warner et al., 2018). Rural labour markets are not any different from the high-end

jobs in developed countries. Unequal pay for similar work executed by women and men and restricted promotion for women are evident in agricultural industries in the developing world (Farnworth et al., 2020; Swain et al., 2019). However, studies on the gender gap in Indian rice mill industries have showed that lower-level leaders were appointed among women workers and the problems raised by women employees were addressed when compared to other informal sectors (Choudhuri, 2018). Therefore, it is important to understand the present situation of gender gap in rice mill industries in Karnataka. Moreover, the influence of gender inequality on work productivity is evident from earlier studies (Bose, 2023). Therefore, the role played by gender gap in influencing various labour-related issues needs to be understood in rice mill industries in Karnataka.

Working conditions can be considered as a major factor because labourers in informal sectors often do not get minimum facilities. Studies have shown that workers in unorganised sectors often do not have any structured house to stay in, work for lengthy hours, do not have any medical insurance and compromise on their health to work in such factories (Cockel et al., 2023). Even most of the labourers working in the unorganised sector do not get any retirement benefits or structured leaves (Acharya & Christopher, 2022; Yagi & Hayashi, 2021). Studies have shown that long working hours have several health impacts and this would affect the abilities of workers (Wong et al., 2019). Therefore, it is important to understand the impact of working conditions of rice mill workers on their work productivity, quality of work and other labour-related issues.

Health-related problems are another important domain under socio-economic conditions. Health hazard-related problems are abundantly observed in rice mill industries (Ansari et al., 2017; Oginyi et al., 2017). The ash particles and mud coming out of rice mills are life threatening for workers (Fatima et al., 2016). Musculoskeletal and respiratory morbidities have been identified to be significant among rice mill workers (M. C. Rana et al., 2018; Roy et al., 2020). Along with these, several health-related problems, such as backache, chronic bronchitis, knee joint pain and allergic bronchitis, are frequently reported by rice mill workers (Nwosu, 2019; M. C. Rana et al., 2018). Lung function tests carried out among rice mill workers along with a population who were not exposed to rice mill dust, showed that the exposed population have a greater prevalence of respiratory diseases (Biswas et al., 2023). Such deterioration in workers' health would pay a toll on the work lives of rice mill workers. Consequently, the quality and productivity of rice mill workers would be affected. Based on this, the following hypothesis was formulated to check whether socio-economic conditions of rice mill workers affect labour-related issues.

H1: Socio-economic conditions significantly influence labour-related issues in rice mill industries in Karnataka.

Moderating role of Covid-19 issues

Covid-19 pandemic caused a severe impact on the socio-economic conditions of people from various sectors (Gössling et al., 2020; Kapasia et al., 2020; Rawal et al., 2020). Some studies have showed the adverse effects of the Covid-19 pandemic as increasing unemployment rate, decreasing wages and cessation of industrial production (Gupta et al., 2022). However, studies are scarce in understanding the moderating role of Covid-19 issues on the relationship between socio-economic issues and labour-related issues. Therefore, the following hypothesis has been formulated to address this issue.

H2: Covid-19 issues significantly moderate the effect of socio-economic conditions on the labour-related issues in rice mill industries in Karnataka.

Figure 1: The conceptual diagram of the present study

3. Methodology

Study design

In the present research, a descriptive and quantitative research approach was utilised to apprehend the socio-economic effects of public policies on labour issues in the rice mill industry.

Instrument

In the context of the type of instrument, a questionnaire was prepared to gather information related to socio-economic conditions (wage issues, gender inequality, working conditions, and health problems) of labourers, Covid-19 issues and labour-related issues of workers engaged in rice mill industries in Karnataka. The first part of the questionnaire dealt with rice mill workers' demographic details, such as gender, age, level of education, marital status, number of dependents, type of employment, and number of years of experience. The second section was based on socio-economic factors, Covid-19 and labour-related issues.

Statistical analysis

The demographic information was represented in a tabulated format by percentage and frequency. Partial-least-squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) analysis was adopted for the present study. It was used to test the proposed hypothesis. In terms of the structural model, the path coefficients and the coefficient of determination (R^2) were measured. Finally, a p value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

4. Results

Demographic details

The demographic characteristics of participants are presented in Table 1. Out of 200 participants, male employees (74%) with an age group of 31-40 years (53%) were predominant, highlighting a gender imbalance within this occupation. The age distribution reveals that a significant portion (53%) falls within the 31-40 age range, indicating a predominantly young workforce. However, only 2.5% are aged over 50, suggesting limited representation of older workers in this industry. Most of the respondents have not gone through any traditional educational process (70.5%) and the majority of them are married (65%). Moreover, most of them have more than one dependent family member (91.5%), but they are mostly seasonally employed (72%). The majority of the participants have 5 to 10 years of experience as mill rice workers.

Table 1 Demographic details

	Frequency (n=200)	Percentage
Gender		
Male	148	74.0
Female	52	26.0
Age (years)		
21-30	59	29.5
31-40	106	53.0
41-50	30	15.0
>50	5	2.5
Marital status		
Married	130	65.0
Unmarried	70	35.0
Education		
Illiterate	141	70.5
SSC/HSC	56	28.0
Graduation	3	1.5
Number of dependents		
Nil	17	8.5
1-2	97	48.5
3-4	67	33.5
>4	19	9.5
Types of employment		
Permanent	49	24.5
Seasonal	144	72.0
Contract	7	3.5
Experience as a rice mill worker (years)		
<5	49	24.5

	Frequency (n=200)	Percentage
5-10	107	53.5
10-15	30	15.0
>20	14	7.0

Reliability and validity in Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

The validity, reliability statistics, and collinearity of the model are demonstrated in Appendix (Table A1). The internal consistency or the reliability of a set of items under each factor or latent variable was assessed using composite reliability (CR) and Cronbach's alpha. The threshold value for both CR and Cronbach's alpha are determined as 0.7 which recommends a reliable nature of all items under each construct (Hair & Risher, 2018; Sarstedt et al., 2022). CR and Cronbach's alpha for all the variables in the present study was greater than 0.7 and therefore can be considered reliable. Additionally, average variance extracted (AVE) values were used to derive the convergent validity of the latent variables. AVE is the grand mean value of the squared loadings of a set of indicators and a value greater than 0.5 for each construct can be represented as a good convergent validity (Hair & Risher, 2018). The amount of multi collinearity has been examined using variance inflation factor (VIF) values. VIF values in a range between 1 to 5 advocate a moderate collinearity (Daoud, 2017). Two different criteria were used for comprehending the discriminant validity, i.e., the Fornell-Larcker criterion and the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio. According to the Fornell-Larcker criterion, the square root of AVE for each variable should exceed the correlation of latent variables. In the present study, the Fornell-Larcker criterion is satisfied (Appendix Table A2). The other criterion for discriminant validity, a Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio should be lower than <0.90 to satisfy the criteria (Henseler et al., 2015). In the present study, all the variables showed an HTMT ratio of less than 0.90 (Appendix Table A3).

Model fit

The R square value for labour-related issues is 0.993 in the present study. This indicates that 99.3 % of the variation in labour-related issues among rice mill workers can be explained by various socio-economic conditions, such as wage issues, gender inequality, working conditions and health problems (Appendix Table A4). Model summary and predictive relevance (Appendix Table A5) showed the requisite indices of the structural model. The Stone-Geisser's Q^2 value is a measure to derive the predictive power of the model. It evaluates whether a model correctly predicts data, which are not used in the estimation of model parameters. A Q^2 value of greater than zero suggests predictive relevance and Q^2 values of 0.25 and 0.50 suggest medium and larger predictive relevance in the model (Sarstedt et al., 2020). Therefore, the Q^2 value of 0.294 for the present study is suggestive of a medium degree of predictive power of the model. Also, the model fit indices suggest a good fit for the model as suggested by the value of standardised root mean square residual (SRMR) to be < 0.08, and NFI to be >0.8. Additionally, the f^2 values suggestive of the 'effect size' indicate the influence of exogenous constructs on the endogenous constructs (Appendix Table A6). The f^2 values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 suggest a small, medium and large effect size, respectively. It shows that socio-economic factors ($f^2 = 0.002$) had a small effect on the labour-related issues in the rice mill industries.

Hypothesis testing

In the proposed model, following the T-statistic, a t-value greater than 1.96 was considered significant. In the present study, socio-economic factors (t-value = 10.939, $p < 0.01$) significantly and positively influence the labour-related issues (Table 2). Furthermore, the moderating effect of Covid-19 issues (t-value = 3.244, $p < 0.01$) were significant on the relationship between socio-economic factors and labour-related issues among the workers in the rice milling industry in Karnataka. Therefore, all the hypotheses taken for the study are supported.

Table 2 Path coefficients

	Path coefficient (β)	t	p value	Decision
Socio-economic factors -> Labour-related issues	0.674	10.939	0.000	Positive and significant
Covid-19 issues -> Labour-related issues	0.031	0.564	0.573	Positive and insignificant
SEF \times CI -> Labour-related issues	0.140	3.244	0.001	Negative and significant

5. Discussion

Work occupies a prominent place in the lives of humans. One needs to labour and earn to maintain expenses and have a sustained life. Understanding working conditions of workers in unorganised and informal sectors is important to achieve a sustainable life for all (Brill, 2021). A thorough research on rice mill workers in Karnataka aids the study to

shed light on the less exposed domain in labour research, especially from developing countries. In general, India and other South Asian countries are patriarchal societies and have a higher workforce from the male population (Khan et al., 2021; Tama et al., 2018). In the present study, similar results were observed, as male employees were higher in number than female employees. Furthermore, the educational background of rice mill workers was similar, as reported by studies conducted on different industries. Earlier studies conducted on tea estate labourers from Darjeeling, India, showed low educational backgrounds restricted these workers from having work flexibility and higher earnings (Lama, 2022).

The present study found that wage issues are significantly troublesome for rice mill workers in Karnataka. Workers and employees struggle with low wages, delayed wages and discrimination of wages. Rice mill workers often do not get any opportunity to assess credits or loan facilities for emergencies. The scenarios are similar as presented by earlier researchers in different areas in developing regions. Lower wages are observed abundantly among workers, especially female workers, who get lower wages than male workers (Puder, 2019; Smart, 2021). Furthermore, the present study showed that one of the sub-factors of socio-economic conditions, i.e., wages, significantly and positively influenced labour-related issues. Therefore, it can be understood that wage-related problems significantly lower productivity and quality of work life of employees. This finding is in line with other studies where wages were identified as a significant factor for determining employee turnover rate, workers' productivity and overall well-being of workers (Edirisinghe & Manuel, 2019; Iwakiri et al., 2023; Policardo et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the effect of gender inequality on work productivity and quality of work life is evident from earlier studies (Bose, 2023). Studies on mill workers showed that unequal pay was prevalent for similar work executed by women and men (Swain et al., 2019). In addition, prior studies have shown that women are majorly replaced by machines and women workers are not much preferred by automated industries, such as rice mills (Khan et al., 2021). Studies conducted on rice mills in Bangladesh have demonstrated that the proportion of women workers is less in fully automatic sectors of rice milling industries and the number of women labourers are slightly higher in semi-automatic rice mills (Kabir, 2017). In the present study, gender inequality was extremely evident and a small number of women workers engaged in rice mill industry did not get proper salaries, lacked respect in their workplaces, and did not get any other benefits. Such gender inequality has been identified to be a significant factor in influencing labour-related issues in the present study.

In addition, rice mill workers in the present study worked in impoverished working conditions where they had to work for long hours without adequate breaks and meals. They did not get structured paid leaves and mostly had to travel long distances for the commute. Furthermore, they did not have job security and they mostly worked in a contractual mode. The scenario was similar to earlier studies conducted on labourers' plight in developing countries. Earlier studies have shown that most of the workers worked for extended hours and did not get any structured leaves and retirement benefits (Acharya & Christopher, 2022; Cockel et al., 2023). Even developed countries, such as Japan and the USA, do not have fixed working hours for people engaged in agricultural sectors (Kunitake, 2016; Leschak, 2008). Earlier studies have shown that workers do not have any access to rest, proper sanitation facilities, or meals (Tama et al., 2018). The present study showed that working conditions significantly influence labour-related issues in rice mill industries in Karnataka.

In addition, the present study revealed that the health status of rice mill workers is not in a good state. The study showed that workers do not get any health insurance benefits for accidents, experience fewer sanitation facilities, and suffer from physical pain and diseases due to prolonged working hours. This is in line with previous studies suggesting several serious health problems caused by working in rice mill industries (M. C. Rana et al., 2018; Roy et al., 2020). Studies have statistically shown the correlation between dust exposure of mill workers and their reduced capacity for pulmonary function. Furthermore, it was evidenced that lack of proper workplace environment, such as, inadequate ventilation, lack of exhaust fan for air circulation, and lack of proper protective gear for workers enhanced dust exposure to workers (Suryadi et al., 2021). Earlier studies have pointed out that workers are not generally aware of the negative effects of the working environment in rice mills. A study on female workers of rice mills in Nigeria revealed that they hardly used any of the protective devices to keep themselves away from occupational hazards (Nwosu, 2019). Furthermore, the present study suggested a significant influence of health problems on labour-related issues, such as work productivity, quality of work life, associated risks, and employee turnover rate. This is in line with previous studies from different industries that show that occupational health and safety issues negatively influenced employee turnover rate (Liu et al., 2019; Nwosu, 2019).

Furthermore, the study demonstrated that the Covid-19 issues significantly and negatively moderated the effect of socio-economic problems on labour-related issues. The study pointed out that during the Covid-19 pandemic, workers suffered due to lack of money, lengthy period of unemployment, problem in commuting, and lack of skilled labourers.

Limitations

The study has a few limitations. Firstly, the study is conducted on a small sample size from a restricted area of Karnataka. In order to understand the socio-economic condition from a broader perspective, future research should incorporate a larger population from various labour industries. Furthermore, the study population has a small number

of women workers and the present research used the current data and tried to understand gender inequalities experienced by workers. In order to understand the scenario extensively, further research should be conducted on women workers in this industry.

Recommendations

The rice mill industries should pay more attention to workers' health conditions and work stress. Personal protective equipment, such as proper masks or respirators, should be used instead of personal clothes or towels as a preventive measure. Some of the basic facilities, such as medical insurance for accidents, sick leaves, and credit facilities or loans, should be provided by companies. These industries should pay attention towards wage issues and other basic amenities, such as food, lodging and healthy working environment, for both permanent workers and contractual workers. Overall, the government should be strict in formulating policies for contractual employment and working conditions of workers.

6. Conclusions

The present study was conducted on rice mill workers in Karnataka to understand the factors influencing labour-related issues, such as work productivity, quality of work life, labourer turnover and health and safety risks, in the work areas. The study showed that wage issues, gender inequality, poor working conditions, and health problems caused by the mill's environment significantly and positively influenced labour-related issues. Therefore, the study discusses various socio-economic conditions of rice mill workers. Workers in rice mills in Karnataka struggle with low wages, gender discrimination in wages, and delayed wages. Rice mill workers often do not get any opportunity to assess credits or loan facilities for emergencies. It was identified that mill workers had to work for elongated hours without any adequate breaks and meals. Lack of structured paid leaves and long-distance commutes inhibited them from having a balanced life. Furthermore, they did not have job security and they mostly worked in a contractual mode. Less number of women employees was engaged in the mill industries and gender inequality was prevalent in payments and working conditions. Furthermore, the workers experienced substantial health issues that significantly inhibited their work productivity and quality of work. In addition, the study demonstrated that Covid-19 issues significantly moderated the effect of socio-economic problems on labour related issues.

REFERENCES:

1. Acharya, S. S., & Christopher, S. (2022). Caste, Covid-19, and Inequalities of Care. In S. S. Acharya & S. Christopher (Eds.), *Springer*. Springer Nature Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-6917-0>
2. Alam, M. N., Alias, R. B., & Hassan, M. D. M. (2019). Impact of social compliance on employee motivation: An empirical evaluation. *Test Engineering and Management*, 81(11–12), 3512–3520.
3. Alam, M. N., Hassan, M. M., Bowyer, D., & Reaz, M. (2020). The effects of wages and welfare facilities on employee productivity: Mediating role of employee work motivation. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 14(4), 38–60. <https://doi.org/10.14453/aabfj.v14i4.4>
4. Ansari, M. M. H., Karim, M. R., & Mashud, I. (2017). Symptoms of respiratory health problems in rice mill workers of Bangladesh. *KYAMC Journal*, 7(2), 758–761.
5. Barhate, B., Hirudayaraj, M., Gunasekara, N., Ibrahim, G., Alizadeh, A., & Abadi, M. (2021). Crisis Within a Crisis: Migrant Workers' Predicament During Covid-19 Lockdown and the Role of Non-profit Organizations in India. *Indian Journal of Human Development*, 15(1), 151–164. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0973703021997624>
6. Bennett, C. L., Raja, A. S., Kapoor, N., Kass, D., Blumenthal, D. M., Gross, N., & Mills., A. M. (2019). Gender Differences in Faculty Rank among Academic Emergency Physicians in the United States. *Academic Emergency Medicine*, 26(3), 281–285.
7. Biswas, M., Pranav, P. K., & Nag, P. K. (2023). Effect on pulmonary functions of dust exposed rice mill workers in comparison to an unexposed population. *Work*, 74(3), 945–953. <https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-205146>
8. Bose, S. (2023). The penalty of work from home: gender gap in productivity of unorganised manufacturing firms in India. *Small Business Economics*, 60(1), 351–369. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-022-00637-2>
9. Brill, L. (2021). What Is Decent Work? A Review of the Literature. In *Decent Work* (pp. 11–26). Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-80117-586-920211002>
10. Choudhuri, T. (2018). Status and Role of Women Workers in. *International Journal of Rural Development and Management Studies*, 12(2), 151–167.
11. Cockel, I., Zani, B., & Parhusip, J. S. (2023). 'There will be no law, or people to protect us': Irregular Southeast Asian seasonal workers in Taiwan before and during the pandemic. *Journal of Agrarian Change*, 23(3), 634–644. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joac.12550>
12. Coviello, D., Deserranno, E., & Persico, N. (2022). Minimum Wage and Individual Worker Productivity: Evidence from a Large US Retailer. *Journal of Political Economy*, 130(9), 2315–2360. <https://doi.org/10.1086/720397>

13. Daoud, J. I. (2017). Multicollinearity and Regression Analysis. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 949(1), 012009. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/949/1/012009>
14. Edirisinghe, S. D., & Manuel, S. (2019). Factors Affecting Sales Employee Turnover in Hotel & Travel Industry: A Literature Review. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 24(5), 35–54. <https://doi.org/10.9790/0837-2405073554>
15. Farnworth, C. R., San, A. M., Kundu, N. D., Islam, M. M., Jahan, R., Depenbusch, L., Nair, R. M., Myint, T., & Schreinemachers, P. (2020). How will mechanizing mung bean harvesting affect women hired laborers in Myanmar and Bangladesh? *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(19), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12197870>
16. Fatima, S. A., Yaqub, G., & Iqbal, B. (2016). Detection of VOC in blood of workers of a rice mill and their occupational health and safety conditions. *Journal of Biodiversity and Environmental Sciences (JBES)*, 9(3), 102–111. <http://www.innspub.net>
17. Gao, X., Wen, J., & Zhang, C. (2019). An Improved Random Forest Algorithm for Predicting Employee Turnover. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4140707>
18. Gössling, S., Scott, D., & Hall, C. M. (2020). Pandemics, tourism and global change: a rapid assessment of Covid-19. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 29(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2020.1758708>
19. Gupta, V., Santosh, K., Arora, R., Ciano, T., Kalid, K. S., & Mohan, S. (2022). Socioeconomic impact due to Covid-19: An empirical assessment. *Information Processing & Management*, 59(2), 102810. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2021.102810>
20. Hair, J. R., & Risher, J. (2018). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, December. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203>
21. Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *J. Acad. Mark. Sci.*, 43, 115–135.
22. International Labor Organization. (2014). *Rules of the game: a brief introduction to international labour standards*.
23. International Labour Organization. (2019). World Employment Outlook Social Trends. In *International Labour Office*.
24. International Labour Organization. (2023). *Working Conditions*. <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/dw4sd/themes/working-conditions/lang--en/index.htm>
25. Iwakiri, K., Sotoyama, M., Takahashi, M., & Liu, X. (2023). Organization factors influencing quality of work life among seniors' care workers with severe low back pain. *Journal of Occupational Health*, 65(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/1348-9585.12378>
26. Kabir, M. H. (2017). Development of Rice Milling Industry and Employment Generation : Policy Options for the Betterment of Rice Mill Workers in Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Institute of Labour Studies*, July, 32–52.
27. Kapasia, N., Paul, P., Roy, A., Saha, J., Zaveri, A., Mallick, R., Barman, B., Das, P., & Chouhan, P. (2020). Impact of lockdown on learning status of undergraduate and postgraduate students during Covid-19 pandemic in West Bengal, India. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 116, 105194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.105194>
28. Khan, A. R., Uddin, M., & Sarker, R. (2021). Socio-economic conditions of rice-mills workers : A study on Sherpur district in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Research in Human Resource Management*, 3(1), 51–57.
29. Kim, S. J., & Choi, S. O. (2018). The effects of job mismatch on pay, job satisfaction, and performance. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 4(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc4040049>
30. Kunitake, H. (2016). Agriculture and labor law. *The Japanese Journal of Labour Studies*, 58(10), 69–77.
31. Lama, S. D. (2022). Tea Plantation Workers and the Human Cost of Darjeeling Tea. In (pp.). In *Caste, Covid-19, and Inequalities of Care: Lessons from South Asia* (pp. 333–354). Springer Nature Singapore.
32. Leschak, J. (2008). Food prices soar as farmworkers suffer: agribusiness, government and the denial of farm labor rights. *Regional Labor Review*, 11(1), 24–33.
33. Liu, S., Gyabeng, E., Joshua Atteh Sewu, G., Nkrumah, N. K., & Dartey, B. (2019). Occupational Health and Safety and Turnover Intention in the Ghanaian Power Industry: The Mediating Effect of Organizational Commitment. *BioMed Research International*, 2019, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/3273045>
34. Nelson, L. K., Brewer, A., Mueller, A. S., O'Connor, D. M., Dayal, A., & Arora, V. M. (2023). Taking the Time: The Implications of Workplace Assessment for Organizational Gender Inequality. *American Sociological Review*, 88(4), 627–655. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00031224231184264>
35. Nwosu, I. A. (2019). Work-Health Imbalance among Female Rice Mill Workers in Southeast Nigeria. *The Anthropologist*, 35(1–3). <https://doi.org/10.31901/24566802.2019/35.1-3.2036>

36. Oginyi, R., Mbam, O. S., Abojei, C. O., & James, O. N. (2017). Assessment of occupational health Hazard and the use of safety measures among Rice mill Workers in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 35(7), 1133–1141.
37. Palit, P. N. (2021). Rice milling industries in Burdwan City- A socioeconomic outlook. In *Advances in sustainable development and management of environmental and natural resources*. Apple Academic Press.
38. Pereira, D., Leitão, J., & Ramos, L. (2022). Burnout and Quality of Work Life among Municipal Workers: Do Motivating and Economic Factors Play a Mediating Role? *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(20). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192013035>
39. Policardo, L., Punzo, L. F., & Carrera, E. J. S. (2019). On the wage–productivity causal relationship. *Empirical Economics*, 57(1), 329–343. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00181-018-1428-5>
40. Puder, J. (2019). Excluding migrant labor from the malaysian bioeconomy: Working and living conditions of migrant workers in the palm oil sector in Sabah. *Austrian Journal of South-East Asian Studies*, 12(1), 31–48. <https://doi.org/10.14764/10.ASEAS-0012>
41. Punia, M., Nimbrayan, P. K., & Yadav, K. K. (2021). Problems, Prospects and Policy Recommendations of Crop Insurance Schemes. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, May, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajaees/2021/v39i530572>
42. Rahman, B. A., Rubaiyath, N. M., & Zhang, J. (2023). Trends in rice research: 2030 and beyond. *Food and Energy Security*, 12(2), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fes3.390>
43. Rana, M. C., Naskar, S., Roy, R., Das, D. K., & Das, S. (2018). Respiratory Morbidity among Rice Mill Workers in an Urban Area of Burdwan District, West Bengal: A Cross-sectional Study. *Indian Journal of Occupational and International Medicine*, 22(1), 5–10. <https://doi.org/10.4103/ijoem.IJOEM>
44. Rana, M., Naskar, S., Roy, R., Das, D., & Das, S. (2018). Respiratory morbidity among rice mill workers in an urban area of Burdwan District, West Bengal: A cross-sectional study. *Indian Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 22(1), 5. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijoem.IJOEM_20_18
45. Rawal, V., Kumar, M., Verma, A., & Pais, J. (2020). Covid-19 Lockdown: Impact on Agriculture and Rural Economy. In *Society for Social and Economic Research*.
46. Roy, S., Dasgupta, A., Bandyopadhyay, L., Paul, B., Bandyopadhyay, S., & Kumar, M. (2020). Morbidities of rice mill workers and associated factors in a block of West Bengal: A matter of concern. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 9(1), 359. https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_858_19
47. Sarstedt, M., Hair, J. F., Nitzl, C., Ringle, C. M., & Howard, M. C. (2020). Beyond a tandem analysis of SEM and PROCESS: Use of PLS-SEM for mediation analyses! *International Journal of Market Research*, 62(3), 288–299. https://doi.org/10.1177/1470785320915686/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/10.1177_1470785320915686-FIG2.JPEG
48. Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Hair, J. F. (2022). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling. *Handbook of Market Research*, 587–632. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-57413-4_15
49. Shah, A., & Lerche, J. (2020). Migration and the invisible economies of care: Production, social reproduction and seasonal migrant labour in India. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 45(4), 719–734. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tran.12401>
50. Smart, W. (2021). *Women's Wages*. Good Press.
51. Somavia, J., & General, I. D. (1999). *Decent work*.
52. Suryadi, I., Matin, H. H. A., Suhardono, S., Rinawati, S., Rachmawati, S., & Kusumaningrum, L. (2021). Correlation with dust exposure rice milling worker's lung function capacity in Sub-District Kerjo. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 623(1), 8–12. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/623/1/012033>
53. Swain, M., Das, L., & Hembram, B. R. (2019). Gender Inequality in Rural Labour Market in Odisha: Some Micro Evidence from Dhenkanal District., 38(2), 212–226. *IASSI-Quarterly*, 38(2), 212–226.
54. Tama, R. A. Z., Ying, L., Happy, F. A., & Hoque, M. M. (2018). An Empirical Study on Socio-economic Status of Women Labor in Rice Husking Mill of Bangladesh. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, November, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2018/v2i225835>
55. Warner, J., Ellmann, N., & Boesch, D. (2018). *The Women's Leadership Gap*. Centre for American Progress. <https://www.americanprogress.org/article/womens-leadership-gap-2/>
56. Wong, K., Chan, A. H. S., & Ngan, S. C. (2019). The Effect of Long Working Hours and Overtime on Occupational Health: A Meta-Analysis of Evidence from 1998 to 2018. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(12), 2102. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16122102>
57. Yagi, H., & Hayashi, T. (2021). Working conditions and labor flexibility in non-family farms: Weather-based labor management by Japanese paddy rice corporations. *International Food and Agribusiness Management Review*, 24(2), 249–266. <https://doi.org/10.22434/IFAMR2020.0013>

Appendix

Table A1 Construct reliability and validity

Item	Loadings	Indicator reliability	VIF	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	CR	AVE
Socio-economic factors							
Wage issues				0.788	0.796	0.784	0.550
SF_WI_1	0.645	0.416	1.115				
SF_WI_3	0.808	0.653	1.265				
SF_WI_5	0.762	0.580	1.257				
Gender inequality				0.759	0.778	0.770	0.530
SF_GI_1	0.673	0.452	1.177				
SF_GI_4	0.807	0.652	1.207				
SF_GI_5	0.696	0.485	1.119				
Working conditions				0.732	0.731	0.803	0.577
SF_WC_1	0.779	0.608	1.326				
SF_WC_2	0.777	0.603	1.310				
SF_WC_3	0.720	0.518	1.161				
Health problems				0.775	0.794	0.822	0.607
SF_HP_1	0.777	0.604	1.346				
SF_HP_3	0.706	0.498	1.237				
SF_HP_5	0.848	0.719	1.457				
Labour-related issues							
Productivity and efficiency				0.742	0.765	0.806	0.583
IL_PE_1	0.680	0.462	1.202				
IL_PE_3	0.766	0.587	1.272				
IL_PE_5	0.837	0.700	1.362				
Quality of work				0.715	0.721	0.795	0.564
IL_QW_1	0.781	0.610	1.208				
IL_QW_2	0.762	0.581	1.264				
IL_QW_4	0.708	0.501	1.200				
Labour turnover				0.748	0.757	0.768	0.527
IL_LT_1	0.782	0.611	1.206				
IL_LT_2	0.649	0.422	1.091				
IL_LT_3	0.739	0.547	1.202				
Health and safety risks				0.772	0.783	0.774	0.534
IL_HS_1	0.660	0.435	1.183				
IL_HS_3	0.768	0.591	1.159				
IL_HS_4	0.759	0.577	1.170				
Covid-19 issues				0.701	0.771	0.778	0.539
CI_1	0.688	0.473	1.109				
CI_2	0.764	0.583	1.238				
CI_5	0.748	0.560	1.216				

CR: Composite Reliability

Table A2 Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Covid-19 issues (1)	0.734								
Gender inequality (2)	0.810	0.728							

Health and safety risks (3)	0.319	0.304	0.731						
Health problems (4)	0.428	0.503	0.434	0.779					
Labour turnover (5)	0.295	0.324	0.241	0.409	0.726				
Productivity and efficiency (6)	0.512	0.533	0.316	0.391	0.361	0.763			
Quality of work (7)	0.430	0.447	0.469	0.364	0.287	0.363	0.751		
Wage issues (8)	0.263	0.359	0.251	0.278	0.325	0.372	0.346	0.741	
Working conditions (9)	0.409	0.392	0.506	0.430	0.412	0.476	0.500	0.425	0.759

Table A3 Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Covid-19 issues (1)									
Gender inequality (2)	0.830								
Health and safety risks (3)	0.550	0.550							
Health problems (4)	0.675	0.802	0.688						
Labour turnover (5)	0.527	0.570	0.452	0.666					
Productivity and efficiency (6)	0.829	0.890	0.524	0.595	0.582				
Quality of work (7)	0.710	0.750	0.769	0.567	0.478	0.548			
Wage issues (8)	0.460	0.615	0.423	0.417	0.585	0.583	0.556		
Working conditions (9)	0.682	0.657	0.836	0.652	0.707	0.738	0.802	0.698	

Table A4 R square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Labour-related issues	0.994	0.993
Socio-economic factors	0.992	0.992

Table A5 Model summary and predictive relevance

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Labour-related issues	800.000	564.917	0.294

Overall model fit indices: SRMR = 0.063, d_ ULS = 2.99, d_ G = 2.98, $\chi^2 = 3972.89$, NFI = 0.904

Table A6 F square

	Labour-related issues	Socio-economic factors
Health problems		13.150
Gender inequality		5.277
Wage issues		9.618
Working conditions		14.003
Health and safety risks	6.621	
Labour turnover	10.711	
Productivity and efficiency	16.608	
Quality of work	17.019	

	Labour-related issues	Socio-economic factors
Socio-economic factors	0.002	
Covid-19 issues	0.001	

Figure A1 Measurement model

Figure A2 Predictive relevance

Figure A3 Structural model

